

Measurement of Hydrogen Ion Concentration in Mixed Solvents

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Difficulties in establishment of the universal pH scale based on aqueous solution as a standard have been discussed. Different approaches to measure the hydrogen ion concentration in mixed solvents have been critically examined. A method for the measurement using correction factor based on dilute solution of HClO_4 in mixed solvent as the standard has been recommended for the purpose.

IN recent years, there has been an increasing interest in the study of the behaviour of electrolytes in mixed solvents. The effect of solvent-structure and solute-solvent interactions on equilibrium constants and rate constants of chemical reactions in mixed solvents is not well understood. Addition of organic solvents to water brings about a radical change in the properties of the medium. Theories¹ of the structure of water, an extensively used and studied solvent, are inadequate and this is further complicated by the addition of organic components. It is now agreed that the thermodynamics of solute-solvent interactions will help in throwing more light on the nature of ionic solutes and that a knowledge of the reaction rate also would be needed. Attempts are being made to identify the factors determining specific solvation of ions. Inadequate models for the structure of solvents and an incomplete understanding of the forces in the immediate vicinity of the surface of the ions make the theoretical treatment² of the problem of solvation difficult.

Acid-base equilibria are particularly suited for such studies. The effect of solute-solvent interactions on chemical equilibria can be investigated both by alteration of the solvent composition and by variation of solute structure and charge type. So has there been, in recent times, an increasing interest in the determination of the dissociation constants in different mixed and non-aqueous solvents. These, in turn, necessitate the accurate estimation of hydrogen ion concentration in the mixed media. The estimate of hydrogen ion concentration in different solvent may ultimately help in defining a unique standard

retaining aqueous standard, a medium in which so extensive work have been carried out.

The transfer-energy of proton is a quantity of great importance for the establishment of scales for the Bronsted acidity as it gives the numerical expression to the relative availability or activity of protons in two media of different composition and is probably the best measure of the relative basicities of the two solvents.³

The method for the determination of H^+ ion activity in aqueous solution is well known. The cell commonly employed for the purpose is,

Pt, H_2 (g) : Solution (S) or (X) | KCl (conc.) :
(or Hydrogen responsive
glass electrode) Hg_2Cl_2 , Hg.

The biggest drawback in this set-up is the presence of the liquid junction potential of uncertain magnitude which is practically impossible to eliminate. Assuming that the liquid junction potential is small and that there is no variation of the junction potential when the standard solution is replaced by the unknown solution, the expression for the pH of the unknown solution is given by $\text{pH}(\text{X}) - \text{pH}(\text{S}) = (E_x - E_s) / (RT \ln 10) F$. The validity of the assumption about the liquid junction potential in defining the operational equation has been often looked upon with reserve although Bates et al.⁴ in their work on reference buffer solutions for pH measurements in 50% methanol say, "In as much as the pH response of many glass electrodes is substantially unimpaired

in 50% methanol and furthermore the liquid junction potential also displays satisfactory reproducibility the glass electrode pH meter can be used". Recently Valensi⁵ reported an extensive study in pH measurement in aqueous media and concludes that the uncertainty introduced in pH measurement through the use of the liquid junction may be as high as 0.026 (pH). In the determination of operational pH of the media (X), the pH of the standard buffer should be as close and both the solutions should be equi-conducting (equitransporting). This poses a problem in the determination of pH of solutions with mixed solvents.

In this short review, we are particularly interested in surveying the methods used for the actual measurement of hydrogen ion concentration in mixed solvents. For the details of experimental measurements of pH in aqueous solutions readers are referred to standard texts.^{3, 4, 6-9} Only those aspects that relate to the mixed media will be discussed.

For a given species, *i*, originally present in aqueous medium, when the composition of the medium is changed by addition of an organic constituent, the ratio of ${}_w\gamma_i$ to ${}_s\gamma_i$, where ${}_w\gamma_i$ and ${}_s\gamma_i$ are activity coefficients with reference to infinitely dilute aqueous solution and infinitely dilute solution in solvent 'S', is called the 'medium effect', designated by ${}_m\gamma_i$.

Thus we have by definition, ${}_w\gamma_i = {}_s\gamma_i \cdot {}_m\gamma_i$. has a value different from unity whenever the solvent differs from pure water and is constant so long as the solvent composition remain fixed. With medium effect, thus defined, we have,

$$p_{a_H} = p_{a_H}^* - \log {}_m\gamma_H$$

where $p_{a_H}^*$ is the one referred to the standard state 'S' and p_{a_H} that in pure water regardless of the solvent composition. A general pH scale needs a knowledge of ${}_m\gamma_H$ which means the work of transforming a single ionic species from one medium to the other. Although non-thermodynamic, the values of ${}_m\gamma_H$ in methanol-water and ethanol-water have been calculated by different authors^{4,10}. As has been pointed out by Bates,⁴ "although these results are of considerable qualitative interest, the agreement is not sufficiently good to justify their use in the establishment of reference values of p_{a_H} in alcohol-water solvents". Therefore, at present it seems desirable to define the practical pH scales in terms of p_{a_H} . The operational pH is thus defined exactly in the same way as

$$pH^*(X) = pH^*(S) + \frac{E_x - E_s}{(RT \ln 10)/F}$$

in case suitable buffers to be used as standards in different mixed solvents are available. Although $pH^*(S)$ values for number of standard buffer solutions in methanol, methanol-water systems, in ethanol and ethanol-water systems have been determined by Bates et al.^{4,8}, de Ligny et al. and Gelsema et al.¹¹⁻¹⁶, it is not sufficient for the wide range of mixed solvents. In view of the lack of suitable buffers to be used as standards in mixed solvent, other approaches to the determination of hydrogen ion activity have been made.

The measurement of H^+ ion concentrations in mixed solvents is associated with a number of difficulties. These are :

- (i) The glass electrode potential changes in going from an aqueous to mixed solvents.
- (ii) Liquid junction potential of uncertain magnitude which increases with the increase in the percentage of the organic component may vitiate the results appreciably.
- (iii) The solubility of an electrolyte decreases when the percentage of the organic solvent in the mixed medium becomes high.
- (iv) The sensitivity of the glass electrode decreases as the percentage of organic component increases ; and
- (v) Activity coefficients calculated on the basis of Debye-Huckel equation may differ considerably from the true values.

For measuring the acidity in dioxane-water mixtures, Van Uitert¹⁷ calibrated the glass electrode in the following way. The meter readings in mixed solvents are referred to as 'B' values. The glass electrode was calibrated against $10^{-4}M$ HCl in aqueous solution. The correction factor $\log U_H$ was calculated from the relationship,

$$-\log [H^+] = B + \log [U_H]$$

where $[H^+]$ is the stoichiometric hydrogen ion concentration assuming 100% dissociation of the acid in the aqueous and in the mixed solvents. Bates and coworkers and de Ligny¹¹⁻¹⁵ and coworkers

have approached the problem in light of medium effect already referred to and have made extensive contributions. Both the groups suggest the use of correction factor defined in different ways.

Bates et al.³ defines the correction factor 'δ', as $\delta = E_j - \log m\gamma_H = pH - pa_{H^+}^*$.

The aqueous reference solutions with which the glass electrode pH meter is standardised is assigned pH(s) based on standard reference state and the adopted convention about the activity using Debye-Huckel expression. The operational pH obtained for a solution in a non-aqueous or mixed solvents can be expressed, after incorporating the liquid junction potential, E_j , formally in terms of the pa_{H^+} relative to the aqueous standard state as follows :

$$pH = pa_{H^+} + E_j \text{ (} E_j \text{ in pH units)}$$

$$\text{or } p^*H = pH - E_j + \log m\gamma_{H^+} = pH - \delta.$$

de Ligny and coworkers¹² used the following cells in their investigations.

For these two cells emf's are given by,

$$E_s = E_{ref} - E^{\circ}_{glass} - 0.05916 \log a_{H(s)} + E_{j(s)}$$

$$\text{and } E_x = E_{ref} - E^{\circ*}_{glass} - 0.05916 \log a^*_{H(x)} + E_{j(x)}$$

They defined the correction factor 'δ' as.

$$\delta = pH_x - p^*_{H_x} = \frac{(E^*_{j,x} - E_{j,s}) - (E^{\circ*}_{glass} - E^{\circ}_{glass})}{0.05916}$$

where pH_x is on the basis of operational pH definition given by,

$$pH_x = pH_s + \frac{(E_x - E_s)}{0.05916} \text{ at } 25^{\circ}$$

In order that 'δ' becomes meaningful, it is necessary to have ;

(i) $(E^*_{j,x} - E_{j,s})$ should be a function of the solvent composition only and should not depend

on the nature of the buffering solute in the solutions X and S ;

(ii) $(E^*_{j,x} - E_{j,s})$ should not depend on the type of liquid junction forming device ; and

(iii) $(E^{\circ*}_{glass} - E^{\circ}_{glass})$ should not depend on the type of glass electrode.

According to Gelsema, de Ligny, Remijnse and Blijleven the above criteria are valid only under certain conditions.

In view of the difficulties discussed above, a number of workers^{18,19} followed the simple empirical procedure suggested by Van Uitert et al. Irving and Manhot¹⁹ considered the effect of ionic strength and determined the correction factor $\log U^{\circ}_H$ at zero ionic strength. All these workers used HCl solutions and assumed complete dissociation of HCl also in mixed solvents. HCl, however, is known to be associated to a large extent in solutions having high percentages of alcohols or dioxane²⁰. In work from this laboratory, Pal, Bhattacharyya, Lahiri and Aditya²¹⁻²⁴, and Hazra²⁶, therefore, preferred to use $10^{-4} M HClO_4$ solution as standard in the measurement of H^+ ion concentration in mixed solvents. $LiClO_4$ is completely dissociated in dioxane. Recent experimental results indicate some association in case of $KClO_4$, $CsClO_4$ ²⁵. At high concentration of the organic component, there may be some association in case of $HClO_4$ acid also and as such there may be some deviations.

To check the applicability of the use of $10^{-4} HClO_4$ acid solution as a standard, Bhattacharyya et al.^{21,22} measured the H^+ concentration of formic acid and formate buffers in dioxane water media and compared the values (after appropriate corrections for ionic strengths in mixed solvents using Debye-Huckel equation) with the values obtained on the basis of Harned's work.

The results agreed well upto 70% by wt. of dioxane. For 82% dioxane although there was a difference with Harned's results, the agreement with the data of Danyluk, Taniguchi and Janz was better (a difference to the extent of 0.50 pH unit still remained). This method has been used in this laboratory for measurement of hydrogen ion in ethanol-water, methanol-water, isopropanol-water and dioxane-water mixtures. Taking all precautions, the correction factor for different mixed solvents have been determined. These are presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1—CORRECTION FACTOR* FOR THE MEASUREMENT OF pH IN MIXED SOLVENTS.

Wt. % of methanol	Correction factor in pH units.	Wt. % of Ethanol	Correction factor in pH units	Wt. % of Isopropanol	Correction factor in pH units	Wt. % of Dioxane	Correction factor in pH units
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
8.0	-0.01	8.0	-0.02	8.0	-0.01	10.3	+0.02
16.4	-0.03	16.4	-0.04	16.3	-0.02	20.5	+0.03
25.2	-0.03	25.3	-0.05	25.1	-0.03	30.6	+0.05
34.4	-0.06	34.4	-0.09	34.3	-0.07	40.7	+0.07
44.1	-0.12	44.0	-0.17	43.9	-0.14	50.8	+0.13
54.2	-0.18	54.1	-0.27	54.0	-0.20	60.7	+0.29
64.7	-0.25	64.7	-0.33	64.6	-0.23	70.6	+0.49
75.9	-0.23	76.0	-0.30	75.8	-0.21	80.5	+1.00
87.6	-0.14	87.6	-0.18	87.5	+0.04(?)	90.3	+1.86

* Actual pH values in mixed solvents are obtained by algebraic addition of the correction factors to the observed meter-readings provided the solution is dilute.

It is desirable to have a comparison of the correction factors with those given by other workers in this field. A comparison of the correction factors in isopropanol water is not possible as no data are available. The results tabulated below gives an idea about the agreement between the correction factors in other solvents.

DIOXANE-WATER MIXTURES

METHANOL-WATER SYSTEM					
De-Ligny et al. ¹²	Bates et al. ⁸	Present work			
% of alc. by wt.	δ * in pH units.	% of alc. by wt. in pH units	$E_j - \log m\gamma H^*$	% of alc. by wt.	$\log UH^{\circ+}$ in pH units
43.30	0.11	8.1	0.002	8.00	-0.01
64.00	0.22	16.3	0.004	16.4	-0.03
94.29	-0.86	33.3	0.051	34.4	-0.06
		52.1	0.130	44.1	-0.12
		68.1	0.121	54.2	-0.18
				64.7	-0.25
ETHANOL-WATER SYSTEM					
30.00	0.11	16.2	0.003	16.4	-0.04
		33.2	0.086	34.4	-0.09
50.00	0.29	52.0	0.221	44.0	-0.17
71.89	0.33	73.4	0.196	54.1	-0.27
		85.6	-0.032	64.7	-0.33
				76.0	-0.30
				87.6	-0.18

Mole-frac. of org. solvent	$\log U^{\circ H}$ Irving et al. ¹⁹ at 30°	Van Uitert ¹⁷ et al. at 30°	Mole frac. of org. solvent	$\log U^{\circ H}$ present work at 25°
0.05	0.06	0.02	0.05	0.03
0.10	0.12	0.07	0.08	0.05
0.15	0.20	0.13	0.12	0.07
0.20	0.32	0.27	0.17	0.13
0.25	0.48	0.44	0.24	0.29
0.30	0.73	0.67	0.33	0.49
0.35	0.99	0.90	0.46	1.00
			0.65	1.86
			0.65	1.86

The agreement between the correction factors in the present work and those reported by deLigny et al. and Bates et al. is good over a limited range. For high percentage of organic solvents there is difference in the values of the correction factors reported by these two groups.

* values are to be subtracted from the meter readings
+ values are to be added algebraically to the meter-readings.

Van Uitert et al. and Irving et al. determined the correction factors in dioxane-water mixtures using HCl and NaCl mixtures at different concentrations but at constant ionic strength of 0.1 M and calculated $\log U_{\text{H}}^{\circ}$ (correction appropriate to zero ionic strength) values using $-\log [\text{H}^+] = B + \log U_{\text{H}}^{\circ} + \log \gamma_{\pm}$

Values of $\log \gamma_{\pm}$ for HCl were taken from Harned and Owen's²⁰ data. The $\log U_{\text{H}}^{\circ}$ values of Irving et al. and Van Uitert et al. are in very good agreement. The present work shows that the $\log U_{\text{H}}^{\circ}$ values are in good agreement when the percentage of organic solvent is low whereas the values at high percentages differ considerably. This is likely because of greater association of HCl compared to HClO_4 in high percentages of organic solvent.

The investigations from this laboratory show that the use of obtaining correction factor following modified Van Uitert procedure using HClO_4 acid can be conveniently adopted for measuring hydrogen ion concentration in mixed solvents specially in view of the fact that the standard buffers in mixed media are only few and our knowledge about medium effect is limited. However, as pointed out by Bates,³ we also feel that the application of the correction terms once determined may not constitute a procedure of highest accuracy. It is desirable that the correction factor should be determined at the beginning and the end of each set of measurements where higher accuracy is desired.

The glass electrode should be replaced every three to four months as it loses in sensitivity and more quickly in mixed solvents. However, the life of the electrode may be, to some extent, prolonged if after each set of measurements the electrode is dipped in concentrated HCl for about ten minutes, washed and then stored in distilled water. It should be borne in mind that in general sensitivity changes as one goes from water to mixed solvents. It is desirable that the performance of the electrode be checked with two standard buffers in mixed solvents.

We conclude with a remark by G. N. Lewis²⁷ in 1923, "At the present time we must conclude that the determination of the absolute activity of ions is an interesting problem but one which is yet unsolved". Our present status of knowledge has not been able to solve this. More extensive studies may throw light on the problem and pave the way for a uniform stand-

ard state in different mixed solvents based on aqueous standard.

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